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- **Resumen:**

Objective: To determine the in vitro antimicrobial effects of 3 endodontic sealers AH Plus, Sealapex, and Tubli-Seal on *Actinomyces radidentis*, a bacterial species commonly found in root canals.

Methods: Prior to the experimental procedures, bacterial identification tests, such as Gram staining, catalase, and API 20A, were performed, and the bacteria were identified as *A. radidentis*. The agar diffusion susceptibility test was performed to determine the areas of bacterial growth inhibition and, consequently, the microbial resistance of the 3 sealers against *A. radidentis*. Chlorhexidine was used as a positive control, and saline solution was used as a negative control.

Results: Tubli-Seal cement had an average diameter of inhibition zones in the 3 panels of 22.73 mm, that of AH Plus was 17.13 mm, and that of Sealapex, 11.99 mm. A one-way ANOVA test showed that there were significant differences between the 3 cements ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Tubli-Seal showed the highest levels of antimicrobial activity, which was followed by AH Plus with the next highest levels and, finally, Sealapex with the lowest levels of antimicrobial activity.

- **Proyecto de investigación:**

"Efecto antimicrobiano de tres cementos de conductos contra actinomicas radidentis: estudio in vitro" aprobado el 5 de septiembre de 2003 en el ambito de la Unión Europea y financiado por Egas Moniz-cooperativa de enseñanza superior.